

Data set of measurement data vs test conditions for IT performance characterised in presence of separate and combined influence factors

Partner	LNE
Measured power quality parameter	Accuracy of voltage transformers
Influence factor 1	Temperature
Influence factor 2 (if combined with 1)	Vibration
Influence factor 3 (if combined with 2 and 3)	Harmonics
Index used to compare the reference power quality parameter with the measured power quality parameter	<p align="center">Ratio Error at 50 Hz</p> $\varepsilon = 100 \cdot \frac{k_n U_s - U_p}{U_p}$ <p align="center">Phase displacement at 50 Hz</p> $\Delta\varphi = \varphi_s - \varphi_p$
Transducer under test	<p>Inductive voltage transformer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rated primary voltage U_p: 35 kV • Rated secondary voltage U_s: 100 V • Nominal ratio $k_n = 350$ • Accuracy class 1 %
Measurement procedure (short description)	<p>The procedure for the characterization of the Voltage Transformer (VT), aimed at assessing the effects of temperature and vibration, is presented below :</p> <p>Temperatures: -25 °C, 23 °C and 55 °C.</p> <p>Voltage: 18 kV, 24 kV and 30 kV.</p> <p>Harmonics : up to 4 kHz (5% of 30 kV up to 2 kHz and 3 % of 30 kV up to 4 kHz)</p> <p>Frequency of vibration: 3 Hz, 20 Hz, 100 Hz and 150 Hz).</p> <p>Acceleration of vibration: 0.1g, 0.3g and 0.5g ($g \cong 9,81$ m/s²).</p> <p>Axis of vibration: vertical (Z) or horizontal (longitudinal X or transversal Y).</p> <p>The chronology of the procedure is stepped below:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The accuracy of the transformer without vibration has been checked for all the three temperatures (-25 °C, 23 °C and 55 °C) 2. The shaker has been set at Z axis 3. The accuracy of the transformer is measured under vibrations for all the three temperatures (-25 °C, 23 °C

and 55 °C) all the vibration frequencies (3 Hz, 20 Hz, 100 Hz and 150 Hz) and all the accelerations (0.1 g, 0.3g and 0.5g)

4. The shaker has been set at X axis
5. The accuracy of the transformer without vibration has been measured at 23 °C
6. The accuracy of the transformer is measured, at 23 °C, under vibration frequencies of 3 Hz and 100 Hz and accelerations of 0.1 g, 0.3g and 0.5g.
7. The shaker has been set at Y axis
8. Step 5 repeated
9. Step 6 repeated
10. The shaker has been set at Z axis
11. The influence of harmonics under vibration has been measured for all the three temperatures (-25 °C, 23 °C and 55 °C) under vibration frequency of 20 Hz and 100 Hz at 0.5g acceleration.

The generation and measurement setup is represented in Figure 1.

Measurement Setup (short description)

Fig 1: Determination of the accuracy of the VT under separate and combined influence factor of temperature and vibration

The generator is based on the use of two step-up VTs arranged in series, one VT to generate the fundamental amplitude up to 30 kV and another VT to generate the harmonic amplitude. Two power amplifiers have been used to feed up both VTs.

The set up include also an electrodynamic shaker for the generation of the vibrations. The shaker can vibrate within three axis, horizontal (X and Y axis) and vertical (Z axis), with vibration frequency ranging from 3 Hz to 2 kHz. The peak-to-peak displacements could be configured from 25 mm to 75 mm.

A climatic chamber has been adapted in such a way that the transformer could be placed over the electromagnetic shaker during the vertical vibration tests.

The measuring system is composed by a high voltage standard divider associated with a Low Voltage Measuring System (LVMS). The LVMS is able to measure accurately the ratio and the phase difference between the output voltages of receptively the standard divider and the VT under test. The LVMS is composed by two sampling voltmeters from Keysight, type 3458A, which are widely used in metrology institutes as an analogue to digital converter for accurate AC measurements. The uncertainties of measurements of the whole measuring system are bout $(0.13 \times f + 20)$ ppm for the ratio error (ppm is a relative value, which means parts per million; $1 \text{ ppm} = 1 \mu\text{V}/\text{V}$) and $(0.13 \times f + 20) \mu\text{rad}$ for the phase displacement.

Main results (tables, plots,...)

The influence of both parameters, temperature and vibration, applied simultaneously, can be analyzed from Figure 2 and 3. The results with or without vibration, at each temperature, show very small deviation. The influence of the two parameters, temperature and vibration, applied simultaneously did not reveal greater effects than when they were applied separately. The results show that highest deviations are obtained et very low temperature but the VT remains at its accuracy class (1 %).

Fig 2: Results of the VT regarding the temperature combined with vibration for the ratio error.

	<p><i>Fig 3: Results of the VT regarding the temperature combined with vibration for the phase displacement.</i></p>
References	<p>Agazar, M.; Istrate, D.; Pradayrol, P. Evaluation of the Accuracy and Frequency Response of Medium-Voltage Instrument Transformers under the Combined Influence Factors of Temperature and Vibration. <i>Energies</i> 2023, 16, 5012. https://doi.org/10.3390/en16135012</p>
Attached files	<p>Name: 19NRM05_VIBTEM_LNE.zip Description: the folder contain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy of VT under vibration at 23 °C and Z axis • Accuracy of VT under vibration at 55 °C and Z axis • Accuracy of VT under vibration at -25 °C and Z axis • Accuracy of VT under vibration at 23 °C and X axis • Accuracy of VT under vibration at 23 °C and Y axis • Accuracy of VT under temperature, vibration and harmonics up to 4 kHz. <p>All the measurement have been done with and without vibration. One for the accuracy test under temperature with or without vibration. The measurement without vibrations (0 Hz) could be taken as a reference for further comparison.</p>
Agree to make the data public ? (yes/no)	yes